

POLLEN VIABILITY- A USEFUL SELECTION CRITERIA FOR SCREENING AGAINST THERMOTOLERANCE IN TOMATO SEEDLINGS

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Abstract

Pollen is the mature male gametophyte being the most sensitive cell type affected by the occurrence of high ambient temperatures. Rise in temperature for 38°C or above, even for short duration as little as 4-hour exposure to 45°C during flowering stage severely affect tomato crop. A field study was conducted with thirty tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicum* L.) genotypes to screen the effect of high temperature on pollen viability at seedling stage in glass house. Results revealed that different genotypes vary in their response to high temperatures. Data analysis showed highly significant differences. Pollen viability percentage varied from 30%-94%. Genotypes like 17903, GSL-198, 10109, 6234, 17869 having maximum values for pollen viability% designated as heat tolerant and genotypes 17862, TO-1057, 10145, SAMRUDHI, TM-1826 having minimum value for pollen viability designated as heat susceptible. These genotypes can be further used as to get more insight into pollen thermo-tolerance mechanisms and be included in further breeding programs.

INTRODUCTION

Pollen viability is related to pollen which is the mature male gametophyte, being the most sensitive cell types that has been viewed extensively (Zhao, et al., (2024). ; Lohani, Singh,, & Bhalla, (2025). Developing microspores and pollen have been known for a long time to be the cells that are most affected by the occurrence of high ambient temperatures. Heat stress is anticipated by four types of sensors viz, 1. unfolded protein response (UPR) in endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and cytosol, 2. cyclic nucleotide-gated calcium channels (CNGC), 3. ROS and 4. histone proteins in the nucleosome. Each sensor stimulates pollen heat

stress response (HSR) through reprogramming of the transcriptome, proteome and metabolome. (Raja et al., 2019; Muller & Rieu, 2016). So development of pollen is one of the most heat-sensitive stages in plants (Ghabileh, Lotfi, Aliniaiefard, & Ramshini, (2024) and main factor in the reduction of crop yield and quality under heat stress condition (Bokshi et al., 2021).

Pollen grains are male gametophyte formed inside specialized organs – the anthers made up of epidermis, endothecium, tapetum and connective tissues. Diploid pollen mother cells within the anther

generate haploid microspores which develop into pollen following two sequential distinct phases, namely microsporogenesis and microgametogenesis. In microsporogenesis diploid pollen mother cells after two meiotic division produce tetrads of haploid microspores which are released as uni-cellular microspore (Giorno et al., 2013). In microgametogenesis, the free microspores after release from tetrad, enlarge and undergo asymmetric cell division known as Pollen Mitosis I (PMI) to develop a larger vegetative cell and a smaller germ cell called the generative cells. The germ cell is then engulfed by the vegetative cell to create novel cell and undergoes a second mitotic division known as Pollen Mitosis II (PMII), either before pollen is released from the anther or during pollen tube growth, to form two sperm cells (Rieu, Twell, & Firon., 2017). The energy for the pollen development is provided by the innermost anther wall layer- the tapetum. It provides nutrients to the developing microspores, enzymes for the dissolution of tetrads and materials required for the synthesis of pollen exine. (Yue et al., 2017). Tapetum is highly associated with microspore development and it degenerates (apoptosis) to release energy shortly after microspores released from the tetrad (Rieu, Twell, & Firon., 2017). Any abnormality in the tapetum directly affects the pollen fertility by producing excessive polyamines (Tariq, Yaseen, Xu, Rehman, Bibi, & Uzair,2023). Heat stress brings about premature degeneration of the tapetum layer. The tapetum is very rich in mitochondria as compared to vegetative tissues. Under HS, mitochondria generate ROS as by-product of aerobic metabolism and cause oxidative damage and cell death. Reactive oxygen species signaling leads to programmed cell death (PCD) of the tapetum. This phenomenon is reported in dicot species such as Arabidopsis, tomato, and tobacco, and in monocot species such as rice (Chaturvedi et al., 2021).

Heat stress treatment decreased pollen viability and inhibited fruit set due to flower wilting and abnormal abscission in thermosensitive cultivar (Zhou et al, 2017). The reduction in plant size was also observed along with reduced pollen viability upon heat stress heat sensitive genotypes (Poudyal, Rosenqvist, & Ottosen, 2019). Studying this trait under heat stress condition is of interest to breeder, agronomist, geneticist aiming to improve existing germplasm

(Mesihovic et al., 2016). Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) grow well at 21-24°C (Graci, S., & Barone, A. (2024). While optimal temperature ranges required at different stages of its development are 15-30°C at germination, 20-24°C for vegetative growth, 14-20°C for fruit set night, 20-24°C fruit set day (Yamaura, Kanno, Takano, Isozaki, , & Iwasaki, 2021). However, a number of reports are available depicting that heat stress can develop at mean daily temperature of 28-29°C (Alsamir, Mahmood, Trethowan, & Ahmad, 2021) . Rise in temperature for 38°C or above, even for short duration (Ghahleleh, Lotfi, Aliniaiefard, & Ramshini, 2024), as little as 4 hour exposure to 45°C during flowering stage severely affect this crop. Continuous exposure to day/night temperature of 32/26°C markedly reduce number of pollen grains by altering carbohydrate metabolism in anther thus decreasing pollen viability (Althiab-Almasaud, Teyssier, Chervin, Johnson, & Mollet,2024). Keeping in view this present research was planned to investigate the effect of heat stress on tomato seedlings.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

The present research was conducted in department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi. Thirty tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicum* L.) accessions (Table 1.) collected from National Agriculture Research Centre (NARC), Islamabad, Tomato Genetics Resource Centre (TGRC), California. and Ayub Agricultural Research Institute (AARI), Faisalabad. Before sowing seeds were dipped in Topsin-M at the rate of 100-150 g per acre/100L to protect seed from powdery mildew. Sowing of tomato nursery was done in nursery trays in media comprised of sand, farmyard manure and clay in ratio of 1:1:1. After 25 days of sowing, seedlings were shifted to pots of size 22×20 cm in glass house. The temperature in glass house was around 45°C to 47°C. Newly opened flowers (10 flowers in total) were collected from 9am to 11am in petri dishes from 5 different plants from each genotype. In lab, pollen viability was determined by following method of Marutani *et al.* 1993. Tapping flowers dispersed pollen on microscope slide which were stained with 1% acetocarmine. From this screening ten genotypes were selected having most diverse values for pollen viability

under heat stress.

Results and discussion

Assessment of pollen viability is critical for the evaluation of pollen germination ability after exposure to certain conditions (Dafni & Firmage, 2000). Pollen are most sensitive stage that effected by heat stress by onset of different cytological alteration during pollen development and pollen tube growth (Chaturvedi, et al., 2021).

Pollen viability of 30 genotypes was assessed after heat stress in glass house. Data analysis showed highly significant differences (P= 0.00 F =26.4) among all genotypes. Pollen viability varied from 30%-94% with a grand mean of 69% (Table 1). The coefficient of variation (CV%) for pollen viability was 9.23 %. Least significant difference Test applied to mean pollen viability of all 30 tomato accessions. Mean performance indicated that the genotype 17903 had maximum (93.9%) pollen viability followed by genotypes GSL-198(92.8%) and 10109 (91.9%). Minimum pollen viability % was observed in genotype TM-1826 that have 30% pollen viability value (Table 1). Reduction in pollen viability was observes Our findings coincide with the results of Zhou et al, (2017)

and Miller et al., (2021). They reported that pollen viability decreased under high temperature and highly significant differences among tomato genotypes exist for pollen viability in their study. As Pollen, being the most sensitive cell types, are most affected by high temperatures (Raja et al., 2019, Paupière et al ; 2017). This is main factor in the reduction of yield and quality under heat stress condition. As tomato genotypes vary in their response to high temperature so screening tomato genotypes for specific stress at seedling stage is main interest to breeder as it corresponds to production (Ghabileh., Lotfi, Aliniaiefard, & Ramshini, 2024). . After measuring pollen viability in 30 tomato genotypes (Appendix A), top 5 genotypes having maximum values for pollen viability% (17903, GSL-198, 10109, 6234, 17869) designated as heat tolerant and top 5 genotypes having minimum value for pollen viability% (17862, TO-1057, 10145, SAMRUDHI, TM-1826) designated as heat susceptible group. (Figure 2.2). The present findings may be useful for breeding tomato genotypes resistant to high temperature stress. In the scenario of global warming the identification of heat tolerant tomato genotypes is of utmost importance for countries greatly affected by heat stress and can be used in future breeding programme.

Table 1.: Mean performance of of tomato accessions for pollen viability (%)

Sr.No	Genotypes	Pollen viability %
1	17903	93.9
2	GSL-198	92.8
3	10109	91.9
4	6234	90.2
5	17869	90.1
6	19890	89.2
7	17878	86.1
8	29510	86.0
9	10194	85.8
10	NAGINA	85.8
11	HT-1914	83.2
12	29448	79.8
13	29628	79.1
14	29522	72.0
15	17889	67.1
16	10196	66.2
17	19292	65.3
18	10104	65.1
19	10111	64.3

20	10122	63.6
21	10138	63.5
22	KORTAJA F1	56.3
23	TEJAS	54.4
24	TO-1057	53.5
25	YAQOOT F1	49.2
26	17862	48.1
27	Rio grande	47.1
28	10145	40.5
29	SAMRUDHI	30.6
30	TM-1826	30.3

Critical Value 10.417

Table 2: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for pollen viability (%)

SOV	Df	SS	MS
Genotypes	29	31199.0	1075.83 **
Error	60	2440.9	40.68
Total	89		

Where * = significant **= highly significant

Figure.2.1: Pollen viability assay of heat tolerant and susceptible tomato genotypes.

a:17903 b: GSL-198 c:10109 d:6234 e:17869
 f:17862 g:TO-1057 h:10145 i: SAMRUDHI j:TM-1826

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